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Human Precision Grip Performance under Variable Skin Friction Conditions: A Modelling and Experimental Study

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to understand the effect of skin friction (μ) on precision grip performance in human subjects using experiment and computational modelling. In particular, the study contrasts two different kinds of change in friction: 1) long-term changes in the form of intrinsic skin friction of individuals, and 2) short-term changes produced by wetting the fingers. The effect of these two kinds of change in friction is studied on four different metrics of precision grip performance: Peak Grip Force (PGF), Steady-state Grip Force (SGF), Safety Margin (SM) and PGF/SGF ratio. The subjects ($n=16$) who participated in this study were divided into two categories, in terms of their intrinsic skin friction, as high friction and low friction subjects. Experimental data shows that though PGF change from dry to wet conditions is non-significant, it shows a significant difference between high and low friction groups. SGF shows a significant change due to dry-wet transition if we combine both high and low friction groups. However, the difference in SGF between high and low

friction groups under wet conditions only is non-significant. The average value of SM was maintained in a very narrow band for all the four categories of interest: low and high μ subjects and for dry/wet conditions. The average PGF/SGF ratio is nearly the same for both low μ subjects and high μ subjects under the dry condition, whereas the ratio is lower for high μ subjects than for low μ subjects under wet conditions. The experimental data was matched to the computational model output, which involves two Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers (a grip force controller and a lift force controller). The plant, which represents the finger-object system, generates the position, velocities and acceleration profiles of the fingers and the objects. The controller parameters are optimised using genetic algorithm (GA). The controllers trained first under dry conditions are only slightly retrained with reduced μ under wet conditions, reflecting the intuitive idea that acute changes in friction do not allow much time for retraining. The trends in the simulated precision grip parameters match those of the experiment robustly.

Keywords: Skin friction, grip force, lift force, genetic algorithm, precision grip

GLOSSARY

μ : coefficient of static friction	τ_{FG} : time constant for the dynamics of F_G
M_o : Mass of object (0.130 kg)	τ_{FL} : time constant for the dynamics of F_L
M_{fin} : finger mass (assumed to be $M_o/10=0.013$ kg)	F_G : Grip force (in N)
g : acceleration due to gravity (9.8 ms^{-2})	F_L : Lift force (in N)
F_{rel} : slip force (in N)	F_{fin} : net force acting on finger (in N)
X_{ref} : reference position (in m)	F_o : net force acting on object (in N)
X_o : object position (in m)	F_f : the frictional force acting at the finger-object interface (in N)
X_{fin} : finger position (in m)	F_n : force normal to the table at the object-table interface (in N)
dX_o/dt : object velocity (in ms^{-1})	F_{slip} : maximum frictional force that can be generated (in N)
dX_{fin}/dt : finger velocity (in ms^{-1})	
E_L : lift error at time t	
E_G : grip error at time t	
dt : step interval (0.001 s)	
$\tau_{E.G}$: time constant for the	

<p>dynamics of E_G</p> <p>$F_{L,PID}$: Lift force generated by the lift force PID controller (in N)</p> <p>$F_{G,PID}$: grip force generated by the grip force PID controller (in N)</p> <p>$K_{P,L}$: proportional gain for lift force controller</p> <p>$K_{I,L}$: integral gain for lift force controller</p> <p>$K_{D,L}$: differential gain for lift force controller</p> <p>$K_{P,G}$: proportional gain for grip force controller</p> <p>$K_{I,G}$: integral gain for grip force controller</p> <p>$K_{D,G}$: differential gain for grip force controller</p>	<p>F_{noslip}: frictional force required for no slip (in N)</p> <p>C_L: cost function for determining PID_{KL}</p> <p>C_G: cost function for determining PID_{KG}</p> <p>σ_x: standard deviation in position from time when object reaches X_{ref}</p> <p>$\bar{X}_{O,M}$: average object position (in simulated lift) from time when the object first reaches X_{ref} to the end of the lift (in m)</p> <p>$\max(X_{O,M})$: maximum height to which the object was lifted during simulated lift (in m)</p> <p>PGF_M: PGF for model lift (in N)</p> <p>PGF_E: PGF for experimental lift (in N)</p> <p>SGF_M: SGF for model lift (in N)</p> <p>SGF_E: SGF for experimental lift (in N)</p>
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INTRODUCTION

Human precision grip (PG) is the ability to hold and dextrously manipulate a small object held between index finger and thumb (Napier 1956). This simple, non-invasive instance of motor performance enables clinical researchers to assess motor function in normal and disease conditions (Müller and Dichgans 1994). Previous studies have focussed on the force generation mechanism (Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1991) and the effect of object's physical characteristics on lifting behaviour (Johansson & Westling 1984; Westling & Johansson 1984; Johansson & Westling 1988; Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1991; Gordon, Forssberg et al. 1991; Forssberg, Kinoshita et al. 1992; Gordon, Forssberg et al. 1992; Eliasson, Forssberg et al. 1995; Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1995; Jenmalm, Goodwin et al. 1998; Saels, Thonnard et al. 1999). Some studies have considered the effect of altered hand-object interface and its friction on precision grip

performance (Johansson & Westling 1984; Westling and Johansson 1984; Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1995; Saels, Thonnard et al. 1999). Others have studied the effect of individual variation in friction on precision grip performance (Andre, Lefevre et al. 2010). It would be interesting to compare the precision grip performance of an individual with intrinsically high skin friction, with that of an intrinsically low friction individual. Similarly one may consider the change in precision grip performance due to an acute change in friction produced by altering the skin surface using sandpaper, silk etc. (Johansson & Westling 1984). We thus have two categories of friction change – 1) a long-term change in the form of intrinsic friction of the individual, and 2) a short-term change in the form of an acute alteration of skin friction. A key motivation of the present study is to contrast the precision grip performances corresponding to these two categories of friction change.

Precision grip performance involves two forces: the grip force (F_G) which prevents the object from slipping, and the lift force (F_L) which lifts the object up. The fingers and the object are coupled through skin friction. Slip occurs when the grip force and/or skin friction are not adequately high.

F_G generation begins with an initial estimate of the object's physical properties like weight (Johansson & Westling 1988; Forssberg, Kinoshita et al. 1992), size (Gordon, Forssberg et al. 1991; Gordon, Forssberg et al. 1992), surface curvature (Jenmalm, Goodwin et al. 1998) and friction (Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1995). Based on these estimates, F_G and F_L are generated and applied to the object. During the lift, F_G is kept sufficiently large to prevent object from slipping, due to its own weight or due to internal (Werremeyer & Cole 1997) and external perturbations (Eliasson, Forssberg et al. 1995). The F_G applied in excess of the slip force (minimum force required to prevent slip) is called the safety margin (SM). F_L and F_G are generated in parallel (Johansson & Westling 1984) to maintain grip stability and minimize the time required during sequential force generation. Prior studies highlighted the role played by friction in PG studies (Johansson & Westling 1984; Westling & Johansson 1984; Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1995; Saels, Thonnard et al.

1999; Andre, Lefevre et al. 2009; Andre, Lefevre et al. 2010). Of the six studies cited, three (Johansson & Westling 1984; Westling & Johansson 1984; Forssberg, Kinoshita et al. 1992) focused on modifying the object surface. Johansson et al. (1984) reported that friction and not texture influences FG. Similarly, Saels et al. (1999) reported that FG increases when the object surface friction is reduced using talc. André et al (2009) demonstrated the changes in grip force performance under different hydration levels by lumping all the subjects together. Such a study does not account for the changes in SGF with the intrinsic μ (when the skin is not artificially hydrated). The study by André et al. (2010) dealt with horizontal point to-point reaching task, which is more complicated than pure grip-lift task as there are sharp movements when the desired target changes.

Models of precision grip lift tasks for motor control exist (Kim & Inooka 1994; Fagergren, Ekeberg et al. 2003; de Gruijl, van der Smagt et al. 2009) but there are none that consider the effect of acute changes in friction (dry-wet transition) on grip force generation. The model proposed by Kim & Inooka (1994) describes a closed loop model for grip force generation, but the model does not explicitly model object dynamics. Fagergren et al. (2003) describe both object dynamics and grip force generation, but do not study the effect of friction changes on grip force generation.

In the present study, we consider the role of individual variation in friction on PG performance. We divide the subjects into “high” and “low” skin friction cases and compare their performances. We also consider the changes in PG performance by acutely altering skin friction. We wish to compare PG forces generated due to long-term property like intrinsic skin friction, with those generated due to acute changes in skin friction. In the study, acute change in skin friction is produced by wetting the fingers with water, which is a simple way of producing an acute change in skin friction. Although evolution of skin friction due to wetting is a complex process, the details of the process do not matter for our study since we produce wetting under identical conditions in all subjects. Therefore, in summary, to study the contrasting changes in precision grip performance due to long-

term and short-term changes in friction, using modelling and experiment is the essence of the present study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Test object

The object used for lifting was constructed using Plexiglas (dimensions 37x50x70 mm; mass 0.117 kg). It contained a load cell for measuring F_G with four strain gauges mounted on a steel plate in bridge configuration. The output signal obtained from the load cell was amplified to obtain an output range of 20N and was conditioned using 16 Hz low pass filter (for calibration details see annexure A). Using the data acquisition card (PCI 6014 National Instruments), the signals were digitized at 1 KHz. Data was acquired in LABVIEW™ 8 at 1 KHz and analysed in MATLAB® 7.

A metallic frame (30 cm height) with marked reference position ($X_{ref} = 0.12$ m) enclosed the object. A touchpad (containing a switch) marked the lift onset and lift completion and also served as a platform for resting the hand between lifts. The object had a slot for loading from the top. The total mass of the object (M_o) with 0.013 kg load was 0.130 kg (1.274 N).

Subjects and procedure

Sixteen healthy right-handed subjects (12 male, 4 female) participated in the study. The mean (\pm SD) age was 35.94 (\pm 8.80) years ranged from 26 to 53 years. The study was explained to the subjects and their informed written consent was taken in their native language. The study was approved by the Christian Medical College, Vellore, Institutional Review Board.

Dry condition

The term dry friction does not mean that the finger was artificially dried or its μ was artificially changed; it means mere absence of water. Every subject participating in the study performed the following steps. The subject first washed his/her hands with soap and tap water. The hands were air dried (for > 2 minutes to prevent the μ variation during trials (Johansson &

Westling 1984) until visible traces of water were absent. The subject then sat on a chair comfortably with his/her right forearm flexed in the anterior direction. The experimenter asked the subject to lift his/her hand off the touch pad, approach the object, grip the object and lift it to a height of 12 cm above the table without tilting the object. After holding the object in stable grip for 6 s, the subject was instructed to decrease the grip force and let the object slip from the grip. The hand was rested again on the touchpad, completing the trial. A 10s interval was maintained between the trials. The object was returned to its original position and its surfaces were cleaned with dry tissue paper to maintain uniformity in conditions. All the commands given by the experimenter were verbal. The subjects learn the lifting task (until they were able to lift the object at an approximately constant rate and the PGF and SGF were almost constant) to minimize the effect of learning. Then they performed six consecutive trials for a load force of 1.274 N.

Wet condition

The experimental procedure for the wet condition remained same as the dry condition with the difference of wetting the finger before each trial. The subjects were asked to sit in the chair in a comfortable position with their forearm flexed in the anterior direction. The subjects were not allowed to wash their hand with soap and water after the completion of the dry task, prior to the wet task. As a preconditioning procedure the fingers (index finger and thumb) were immersed in distilled water for 30 seconds at room temperature for saturating the fingertips with water. One wet trial consisted of the subject wetting the finger in distilled water for 2 seconds and lifting the object (procedure of lifting similar to the dry case). A 10 s interval was maintained between trials during which the object was returned to its initial position and its surface was cleaned with dry tissue paper to maintain uniformity in conditions. Six such trials were performed for each subject. During the entire procedure the subjects were not allowed to wipe or dry the finger and no training was provided. Our experimental wet condition can be closely related to the wet condition reported by Andre et al. (2009).

Estimating skin friction, μ

Coefficient of skin friction (μ) was estimated for every trial in both the dry and wet condition in a similar manner. When F_G is gradually reduced, the F_G at which the object slipped is known as slip force (F_{rel}). Standard slip force-load force method (Eqn. 1) was used for estimating μ (Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1995).

$$\mu = \frac{M_o g}{2F_{rel}} \quad (1)$$

Six consecutive trials were used to determine the average μ for the subject. Dry case μ and wet case μ were independently determined. The subjects were classified as high friction and low friction subjects based on μ obtained in dry condition. Subjects with $\mu_d > 0.8$ were classified as high μ subjects and the rest as low μ subjects. This classification was based on the clustering of the μ in two groups using K-means clustering (cluster centres = 0.64 and 0.97; spread = 0.096 and 0.032 respectively).

Model

Figure 1(a) shows the free body diagram for the finger and object configuration. Figure 1(b) represents the model of nonlinear controllers and the plant in closed loop configuration. A number of studies refer to the force required for lifting the object as load force but, in the current study, we represent it as F_o (the net force acting on object). For simulations MATLAB[®] 7 was used and for statistical analysis Origin[®] 8 was used.

Figure 1. (a) Free body diagram showing forces acting on finger and object, (b) the overview of the model for grip force and lift force generation.

Controller

The current model consists of two Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers, PID_{KG} and PID_{KL} , for F_G and F_L respectively. The controllers received error E_G and E_L respectively as the inputs (Eqn. 2) and (Eqn. 3). E_L denotes the positional error and E_G is the square of velocity of the slip.

$$E_L = X_{ref} - X_o \quad (2)$$

Since slip increases grip force, irrespective of its sign, the following form is used:

$$E_G = \left(\frac{dX_{fin}}{dt} - \frac{dX_o}{dt} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Since E_G in Eqn. (3) above increases as square of slip, smooth E_G to keep the fluctuations low, using the following first order dynamics (Eqn. 4) and use this equation to define E_G instead of Eqn. (3).

$$\tau_{E,G} \frac{dE_G}{dt} = -E_G + \left(\frac{dX_{fin}}{dt} - \frac{dX_o}{dt} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

F_L was calculated using the E_L in Eqn. (5) and F_G was calculated using the E_G in Eqn. (6), by the respective PID controllers, as shown below:

$$F_{L,PID} = K_{P,L}E_L + K_{I,L} \int_0^t E_L(\tau) d\tau + K_{D,L} \frac{dE_L}{dt} \quad (5)$$

$$F_{G,PID} = K_{P,G}E_G + K_{I,G} \int_0^t E_G(\tau) d\tau + K_{D,G} \frac{dE_G}{dt} \quad (6)$$

Note that F_G described in (Eqn. 6) is a nonlinear function of the input state, as it involves a quadratic function of slip (Eqn. 4). Therefore, F_G increases with increased slip, irrespective of the sign of the slip.

If Eqns. (5) and (6) were directly used for force generation, it would give rise to discontinuous, initial increase in forces (F_G and F_L) which is unrealistic. Therefore, in order to prevent this discontinuous force rise, we used the following dynamics to produce F_G (Eqn. 7) and F_L (Eqn. 8) from $F_{G,PID}$ and $F_{L,PID}$ respectively:

$$\tau_{F,G} \frac{dF_G}{dt} = -F_G + F_{G,PID} \quad (7)$$

$$\tau_{F,L} \frac{dF_L}{dt} = -F_L + F_{L,PID} \quad (8)$$

At the beginning of every trial F_G and F_L are reset to 0.

Finger - object interaction model (plant)

The plant receives the inputs (F_L and F_G) from the controllers and calculates the kinetic parameters. F_L and F_G interact with the

object due to friction. A subtle feature of finger-object interaction in precision grip is that both F_L and F_G act at the interface between fingers and the object, obscuring the fact that the two forces have very different origins: F_G is generated by the muscles of the index finger and thumb while the F_L could be arising from the muscles of the wrist and/or elbow. Presently we assumed a simple scenario in which F_L acts on the finger and lifts it; F_G presses the finger to the object and couples it to the object. In this simplified representation, the “finger” may be thought to actually represent the part of the hand (thumb and index finger) that interacted with the object.

The forces acting on finger (F_{fin}) and object (F_o) are given as:

$$F_{fin} = F_L - F_f - M_{fin}g \quad (9)$$

$$F_o = F_f + F_n - M_o g \quad (10)$$

where F_f is the frictional force, M_{fin} is the mass of the finger, g is the acceleration due to gravity, F_n is the normal force and M_o is the mass of the object.

F_{slip} (Eqn. 11) represents the maximum frictional force that can be generated. The frictional force (F_{noslip}) required for “no slip” is given by (Eqn. 12).

$$F_{slip} = 2\mu F_G \quad (11)$$

$$F_{noslip} = \frac{M_o M_{fin}}{M_o + M_{fin}} \left(\frac{F_L}{M_{fin}} - \frac{F_n}{M_o} \right) \quad (12)$$

For derivation of Eqn. (12) see appendix.

Frictional force, F_f and normal force, F_n are given in Eqns. (13) and (14) below:

$$F_f = \begin{cases} F_{\text{noslip}}, & \text{if } F_{\text{noslip}} < F_{\text{slip}} \\ F_{\text{slip}}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$F_n = \begin{cases} M_o g - F_f, & \text{if } X_o = 0 \wedge M_o g > F_f \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

The forces acting on the object and the finger are given as Eqn. (15) and (16).

$$F_o = M_o \frac{d^2 X_o}{dt^2} \quad (15)$$

$$F_{\text{fin}} = M_{\text{fin}} \frac{d^2 X_{\text{fin}}}{dt^2} \quad (16)$$

Determining controller parameters

Parameters of the PID controllers ($K = [K_P \ K_I \ K_D]$) along with time constants ($\tau_{F,G}$ and $\tau_{E,G}$ and $\tau_{F,L}$) were determined by minimizing an objective function that characterized the performance of the PG system. This objective function consisted of several terms, the most important of them being position error. In addition to lifting the object to the desired position, the precision grip system should also match other experimental parameters like peak grip force (PGF) and steady-state grip force (SGF). Separate objective functions, C_L and C_G , were used to train the grip force and lift force controllers.

$$C_L = \sigma_X + \frac{|\bar{X}_{O,M} - X_{\text{ref}}|}{X_{\text{ref}}} + \frac{|\max(X_{O,M}) - X_{\text{ref}}|}{X_{\text{ref}}} \quad (17)$$

$$C_G = \frac{|\text{PGF}_M - \text{PGF}_E|}{\text{PGF}_E} + \frac{|\text{SGF}_M - \text{SGF}_E|}{\text{SGF}_E} + |X_o - X_{\text{fin}}| \quad (18)$$

where, C_L is the cost function for training the F_L controller, σ_X is the standard deviation of the object position, $\bar{X}_{O,M}$ is the mean object position between 3500- 4500 ms obtained from the model, X_{ref} is the reference position, C_G is the cost function for F_G controller, PGF_M is the PGF obtained from the model, PGF_E is the experimental PGF, SGF_M is the SGF obtained from the model, and SGF_E is the experimental SGF.

The main intent behind the formulation of C_L as in Eqn. (17) was to find F_L that would minimize position error, which was represented by the second term on RHS of Eqn. (17). The first term, standard deviation in position, σ_X , was necessary to suppress undesirable fluctuation in position even after the arm had reached the reference position. The third term on the RHS of Eqn. (17) was necessary to suppress unwanted overshoot in position, which was observed in simulations without this term.

The idea behind formulation of C_G as in Eqn. (18) was to produce a grip profile that matches the experimental profile closely. To that end, we include error in PGF and SGF in C_G . The last term on the RHS of Eqn. (18) is included to reduce the slip. (The subscripts M and E refer to “model” and “experiment” respectively).

A single simulated trial consisted of the simulation of the model for 5s of simulated time with step interval =0.001s. The PID parameters, PID_{KL} and PID_{KG} , were trained using Genetic Algorithm (GA) (Goldberg 1989; Whitley 1994). Each individual solution is represented by a trial and the corresponding cost function (C_L/C_G for PID_{KL}/PID_{KG}) was determined. The GA parameters used in training are the number of individuals (= 100), maximum number of generations (= 1000) and elite count (= 4). One of the questions addressed in this modeling study was to find out whether PG control strategies were carried over from dry skin case (higher friction) to wet skin (lower friction) case. Therefore, PID parameters were first trained under dry skin conditions, and then used as initial values for training under wet skin conditions. In the dry case, controller parameters were trained in two stages: PID_{KL} was trained first, followed by $PID_{KG,dry}$. In contrast, for the wet case only $PID_{KG,wet}$ was trained. Note that the plant is nonlinear only because of frictional

dynamics. Under “no-slip” condition, which happens in presence of sufficiently strong F_G , the control problem reduces to simple position control of a mass. Therefore, keeping F_G constant at 10 N ($F_{\text{slip}} = 0.637$ N for $\mu=1$ and $F_{\text{slip}} = 1.274$ N for $\mu=0.5$), was sufficient to achieve “no slip.” Under such conditions PID_{KL} was trained independent of $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,dry}}$. The best result obtained for PID_{KL} was used in the second stage to train $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,dry}}$. The initial runs for $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,dry}}$ showed that the optimal grip force profile could be obtained keeping $K_D=9$, $\tau_{F,G} = 0.06$ and $\tau_{E,G} = 0.8$. Hence these parameters were kept constant and only K_P and K_I were trained for determining the $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,dry}}$ and $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,wet}}$ parameters.

For $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,wet}}$ determination, we kept the PID_{KL} constant across the two conditions (dry/wet) and $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,wet}}$ was obtained by two training methods. The first method of training involved fully training of the parameters where out of 100 individuals, 50 individuals were initialized as $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,dry}} \pm \text{noise}$ and 50 were random (with K_P and K_I ranging between $[0,1000]$), this formed the initial range. The elite count was kept constant at 4 and maximum number of generations was kept constant at 1000. The noise added was between $[-200, +200]$. The simulation terminated if the cumulative change in the fitness function was less than 10^{-6} for 50 generations. In the second stage of training (for wet conditions) only partial training of the $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,wet}}$ was carried out. In this case only 20 individuals ($\text{PID}_{\text{KG,dry}} \pm \text{noise}$) were used. The elite count was kept constant at 4 and noise added was between $[-200, +200]$. In the wet case, to simulate partial training we changed the maximum number of generations to 5 (compared to 50 generations at which the GA typically terminates for $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,dry}}$ condition). Reducing the maximum number of generations and individuals drastically reduced the computational time. Training for $\text{PID}_{\text{KG,wet}}$ was also carried out using GA (Goldberg 1989; Whitley 1994). Advantages of using GA are that, it does not suffer from the problem of local minima, and works for continuous as well as discontinuous fitness functions (Goldberg 1989). However, GA suffers from high computation time, poor convergence and, in some cases, optimal solution may not be obtained. These limitations are usually overcome by defining a smaller state space, defining the fitness

function properly and exploiting the inherently parallel nature of the GA (Goldberg 1989; Whitley 1994).

PGF and SGF calculation

Each simulation trial lasts for 5 seconds. PGF was calculated as the maximum of F_G in the first 1000 ms after the lift onset. SGF was calculated as the average grip force exerted between 3500 ms and 4500 ms after the lift onset. Figure 2 shows F_G profiles for experimental data (1 trial) for two random subjects (S2 and S15) under dry and wet conditions.

Figure 2. Single trial illustration for (a) S2 and (b) S15. The left (right) images are dry (wet) trials. Horizontal bar shows the duration over which SGF is calculated.

RESULTS

Experimental task

Sixteen subjects participated in this study. All of them showed a decrease in μ on wetting the finger (Table 1). It is found that the intrinsic μ (μ under dry condition) is 0.64 ± 0.13 (for low μ

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subjects) and 0.97 ± 0.07 (for high μ subjects) ($p < 0.001$). For the dry-wet transition the μ changes to 0.41 ± 0.08 (for low μ subjects) and 0.46 ± 0.11 (for high μ subjects) $p < 0.001$. Two way ANOVA suggested a significant effect of both intrinsic friction [$F(1,28)=29.5$, $p < 0.001$] and dry-wet transition [$F(1,28)=112.94$, $p < 0.001$] on μ .

Table 1. Table showing the Subject ID (ID), age, type (High /low friction), coefficient of friction (μ) and the corresponding peak grip force (PGF) and steady state grip force (SGF) for both experiment and the simulation (using fully trained PID values for wet case). All Values of PGF and SGF are in N.

ID	Type	Age (yrs)	Dry							Wet						
			Experimental			Simulation (full training)		Simulation % Error		Experimental			Simulation (full training)		Simulation % Error	
			μ_d	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF	μ_w	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF
S1	Low	30	0.41 ± 0.04	2.91 ± 0.53	2.07 ± 0.24	2.90	2.08	0.12	0.54	0.32 ± 0.02	2.78 ± 0.33	2.82 ± 0.49	2.77	2.81	0.31	0.21
S2	Low	52	0.59 ± 0.20	3.66 ± 0.48	2.73 ± 0.35	3.66	2.73	0.03	0.02	0.43 ± 0.10	3.71 ± 0.37	3.00 ± 0.30	3.73	3.02	0.53	0.68
S3	Low	26	0.60 ± 0.07	2.29 ± 0.24	2.66 ± 0.23	2.29	2.67	0.14	0.31	0.53 ± 0.02	2.45 ± 0.59	3.02 ± 0.73	2.46	3.01	0.38	0.06
S4	Low	33	0.65 ± 0.06	3.38 ± 0.86	2.10 ± 0.32	3.38	2.10	0.07	0.33	0.32 ± 0.04	3.97 ± 0.42	2.74 ± 0.34	3.95	2.74	0.42	0.06
S5	Low	32	0.74 ± 0.08	3.85 ± 0.46	2.45 ± 0.18	3.84	2.44	0.26	0.29	0.46 ± 0.06	3.33 ± 0.76	2.83 ± 0.46	3.33	2.83	0.02	0.15
S6	Low	37	0.75 ± 0.11	4.18 ± 0.49	1.72 ± 0.19	4.15	1.71	0.57	0.57	0.47 ± 0.04	3.01 ± 0.12	1.61 ± 0.15	3.00	1.62	0.47	0.47
S7	Low	46	0.76 ± 0.06	3.49 ± 0.40	2.18 ± 0.27	3.48	2.17	0.23	0.33	0.36 ± 0.03	3.68 ± 0.41	2.62 ± 0.10	3.66	2.64	0.51	0.76
S8	High	39	0.88 ± 0.15	3.42 ± 0.38	3.17 ± 0.61	3.40	3.18	0.41	0.21	0.61 ± 0.04	2.49 ± 0.32	2.76 ± 0.11	2.48	2.77	0.44	0.39
S9	High	33	0.89 ± 0.14	2.11 ± 0.31	1.70 ± 0.30	2.10	1.69	0.20	0.22	0.33 ± 0.03	2.93 ± 0.47	3.19 ± 0.26	2.95	3.20	0.53	0.28
S10	High	53	0.93 ± 0.07	3.58 ± 0.74	1.97 ± 0.45	3.57	1.97	0.11	0.01	0.37 ± 0.03	3.88 ± 1.07	2.75 ± 0.43	3.88	2.76	0.19	0.22
S11	High	32	0.94 ± 0.22	3.55 ± 0.48	1.74 ± 0.08	3.55	1.75	0.03	0.71	0.63 ± 0.08	1.95 ± 0.29	1.71 ± 0.37	1.94	1.72	0.32	0.71
S12	High	46	0.95 ± 0.09	3.06 ± 0.42	2.04 ± 0.19	3.06	2.04	0.15	0.10	0.46 ± 0.06	3.11 ± 0.40	2.51 ± 0.22	3.12	2.51	0.06	0.07
S13	High	29	0.97 ± 0.08	2.91 ± 0.32	1.47 ± 0.30	2.90	1.48	0.35	0.39	0.39 ± 0.05	3.43 ± 0.70	2.41 ± 0.36	3.42	2.42	0.11	0.25
S14	High	28	1.02 ± 0.11	2.24 ± 0.53	1.56 ± 0.30	2.24	1.57	0.35	0.47	0.43 ± 0.01	2.95 ± 0.39	2.39 ± 0.23	2.94	2.40	0.34	0.14
S15	High	33	1.05 ± 0.09	2.31 ± 0.16	1.64 ± 0.19	2.29	1.64	0.70	0.17	0.55 ± 0.05	2.67 ± 0.44	2.19 ± 0.32	2.68	2.18	0.25	0.22
S16	High	26	1.07 ± 0.09	2.77 ± 0.40	1.72 ± 0.19	2.77	1.73	0.08	0.25	0.40 ± 0.03	2.38 ± 0.26	2.47 ± 0.21	2.39	2.48	0.25	0.30

The change in PGF due to intrinsic variation and transient variation in μ is shown in Figure 3. Intrinsic PGF is found to be lower for high μ subjects when compared to the low μ subjects but this difference is statistically non-significant ($p=0.118$). PGF did not show significant changes due to dry/wet transition for both low μ and high μ subjects, $p=0.784$ (Figure 3). Using two way ANOVA a significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28)=4.93$, $p<0.05$] and a non-significant effect of dry-wet transition [$F(1,28)=0.102$, $p=0.75$] was observed on PGF.

Figure 3. Comparison of experimental (exp) and simulated (sim) PGF for low μ and high μ subjects under dry and wet conditions. Simulated data shows the result under fully trained (F) and partially trained (P) conditions for $PID_{KG,wet}$. Error bars represent the standard deviation.

SGF is one of the key parameters in measuring the effect of μ on PGP. It is observed that low μ subjects generate a higher SGF than the high μ subjects but the change is statistically non-significant ($p=0.10$) (Figure 4). During the dry-wet transition, a

higher SGF was observed in wet case as compared to dry case ($p < 0.004$). Two way ANOVA show a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction on the SGF [$F(1,28) = 3.06$, $p = 0.09$]. However, the dry-wet transition had a significant effect [$F(1,28) = 9.52$, $p < 0.005$] on SGF.

Figure 4. Comparison of of experimental (exp) and simulated (sim) SGF for low μ and high μ under dry and wet conditions. Simulated data shows the result under fully trained (F) and partially trained (P) conditions for $PID_{KG,wet}$. Error bars represent the standard deviation.

The average safety margin ($SM = SGF - \text{slip force}$) did not show any significant change for intrinsic μ ($p = 0.963$). Also, no significant effect of wetting the fingers (acute change in μ) was observed on SM ($p = 0.875$) (Figure 5). Using two way ANOVA a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28) = 0.005$, $p = 0.94$] and dry-wet transition [$F(1,28) = 1.42$, $p = 0.24$] was observed on SM.

Figure 5. Comparison of experimental (exp) and simulated (sim) average safety margin for low μ and high μ under dry and wet conditions. Simulated data shows the result under fully trained (F) and partially trained (P) conditions for $PID_{KG,wet}$. Error bars represent the standard deviation.

The PGF/SGF ratio (Figure 6) for intrinsic μ does not show any significant change ($p=0.915$). However, the transient (dry to wet) change in μ shows a significant decrease in PGF/SGF ratio ($p=0.003$). Two way ANOVA analysis suggests a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28)=0.14$, $p=0.7$] and a significant effect of dry-wet transition [$F(1,28)=7.83$, $p<0.01$] on PGF/SGF ratio.

Figure 6. Comparison of experimental (exp) and simulated (sim) PGF/SGF ratio for low μ and high μ under dry and wet conditions. Simulated data shows the result under fully trained (F) and partially trained (P) conditions for $PID_{KG,wet}$. Error bars represent the standard deviation.

It is interesting that some subjects generated a F_G profile in which there was no sharp peak followed by a lesser SGF; F_G gradually increased and approached SGF instead. In dry conditions only one subject (S3) exhibited such an effect. Under dry wet conditions, such F_G profile ($SGF > PGF$) was seen for five subjects (S1, S3, S8, S9 and S16) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Single trial study for wet condition for subject S3. The grip force gradually builds up to a steady state value without showing a peak in the short-term ($PGF < SGF$).

Simulation results

We present a computational model that can be used to explain the PGF and SGF values from the experimental data. The simulation parameters (PID_{KL} , $PID_{KG,dry}$ and $PID_{KG,wet}$) were trained using GA (GA convergence is shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9). For a detailed list of PID parameters refer Annexure B (Table A1). Two methods of training were employed for $PID_{KG,wet}$. Following the intuitive idea that not much time is available for retraining in the wet case, we train the PID parameters 1) fully (until convergence) and 2) partially (stop training before convergence) in the wet condition. In the second method which involves partial training, we train $PID_{KG,wet}$ for a small number (=5) of generations compared to the higher (>50) number of generations used in the corresponding dry condition. PID_{KL} parameters are directly borrowed from the dry condition and used in wet condition.

Figure 8. Figure showing the average distance between individuals with number of generations for GA for subject S2 under dry and wet condition (with and without noise).

Figure 9. Figure showing the mean fitness of individuals with number of generations for GA for subject S2 under dry and wet condition (with and without noise).

In the first method (Table 1) which involved fully training (trained for >50 generations) the $PID_{KG,wet}$ parameter it was observed that very low average percentage error (APE) when compared to the experimental wet condition were obtained (APE \pm SD is 0.32 ± 0.16 for PGF and 0.31 ± 0.22 for SGF) with range [0.02 0.76]. In particular, in case of low μ subjects, simulation obtained APE \pm SD for PGF as 0.38 ± 0.16 and SGF as 0.34 ± 0.27 . This error is slightly lesser for high μ subjects with APE \pm SD for PGF as 0.28 ± 0.14 and SGF as 0.29 ± 0.17 .

The second method (Table 2) of training in which partial training was imparted show considerably higher APE \pm SD (2.3 ± 1.33 for PGF and 3.40 ± 1.50 for SGF) with higher range [0.02 6.21] for simulated data. The low μ subject's data had APE \pm SD for PGF as 1.98 ± 1.08 and SGF as 3.19 ± 1.81 whereas for high μ subject's simulated data APE \pm SD obtained was 2.55 ± 1.45 and 1.57 ± 1.18 for PGF and SGF respectively.

Table 2. Comparison of experimental and model F_G parameters (PGF_w and SGF_w) obtained when using $PID_{KG,dry}$ and μ_w ($PID_{KG,dry} + \mu_w$) and partially trained $PID_{KG,wet}$. All Values of PGF and SGF are in N .

SUB	μ_w	Experimental		Simulation ($PID_{KG,dry} + \mu_w$)		Percentage error ($PID_{KG,dry} + \mu_w$)		Simulation (for partially trained $PID_{KG,wet}$)		Percentage error (for partially trained $PID_{KG,wet}$)	
		PGF_w	SGF_w	PGF_w	SGF_w	PGF_w	SGF_w	PGF_w	SGF_w	PGF_w	SGF_w
S1	0.32	2.78	2.82	3.00	2.36	7.91	16.31	2.79	2.79	0.23	0.84
S2	0.43	3.71	3.00	3.63	3.18	2.16	6.00	3.57	3.15	3.91	4.90
S3	0.53	2.45	3.02	2.30	2.77	6.12	8.28	2.47	2.91	1.05	3.55
S4	0.32	3.97	2.74	3.65	2.95	8.06	7.66	3.90	2.78	1.73	1.60
S5	0.46	3.33	2.83	4.59	2.92	37.84	3.18	3.25	2.73	2.44	3.66
S6	0.47	3.01	1.61	4.18	2.04	38.87	26.71	3.09	1.51	2.45	6.21
S7	0.36	3.68	2.62	3.49	2.95	5.16	12.60	3.60	2.58	2.03	1.59
S8	0.61	2.49	2.76	7.66	7.12	207.63	157.97	2.46	2.88	1.12	4.52
S9	0.33	2.93	3.19	3.87	3.07	32.08	3.76	3.02	3.11	3.25	2.35
S10	0.37	3.88	2.75	5.16	2.84	32.99	3.27	4.06	2.64	4.55	3.91
S11	0.63	1.95	1.71	3.68	1.80	88.72	5.26	2.04	1.79	4.53	4.60
S12	0.46	3.11	2.51	5.00	3.34	60.77	33.07	3.19	2.60	2.41	3.32
S13	0.39	3.43	2.41	3.63	2.12	5.83	12.03	3.49	2.39	1.78	0.85
S14	0.43	2.95	2.39	3.19	2.35	8.14	1.67	3.00	2.50	1.75	4.59
S15	0.55	2.67	2.19	2.31	2.20	13.48	0.46	2.67	2.28	0.02	4.26
S16	0.40	2.38	2.47	3.82	2.37	60.05	4.09	2.30	2.56	3.53	3.70

The model was cross validated by simulating the GA 10 times for each subject to obtain optimal PID_{KL} and PID_{KG} values. These PID values were then used to calculate the model outputs [C_L ; mean object position, \bar{X}_o ; peak object position max, X_o , and variance in object position, σ_X for PID_{KL} and cost function for F_G controller (C_G), peak grip force (PGF), steady state grip force (SGF) and slip distance (distance between the finger and object position) for $PID_{KG,dry}$ and $PID_{KG,wet}$]. The mean \pm SD of input parameters and model outputs was computed and plotted for subjects S1 and S16 (refer Figure A1, A2 and A3 in annexure).

Interestingly, if only the μ was changed from dry (μ_d) to wet (μ_w), and all the PID parameters are straight away borrowed from dry condition to wet condition, APE \pm SD obtained for PGF was 38.49 ± 50.07 and for SGF was 18.90 ± 36.97 (Table 2). These errors are very high because of the high range of the percentage errors [0.46 207.63]. It was also observed that lower APE \pm SD was observed for the low friction subjects for PGF (15.16 ± 14.78) and SGF (11.53 ± 7.37) when compared to the high friction subjects PGF (56.63 ± 59.46) and SGF (24.62 ± 48.09), respectively. Actually half of the subjects show percentage error in PGF $< 10\%$, and 10 (out of 16) subjects show SGF $< 10\%$. These results strongly suggest that the model trained under dry conditions can contribute significantly to the model under wet conditions. Therefore, when $PID_{KG,dry}$ is used to initialize PID_{KG} in wet conditions, and partially trained with the altered friction μ_w , (PID_{KL} is the same i.e., $PID_{KL,dry} = PID_{KL,wet}$) accuracy improved dramatically. Further improvement in accuracy was observed when $PID_{KG,wet}$ is fully trained.

Since the simulated data obtained were very close to the experimental data, no significant differences in the ANOVA results was obtained between simulation and experiment. Simulated results also show the intrinsic PGF to be lower for high μ subjects when compared to the low μ subjects. The two way ANOVA suggests that a significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28)=4.93$, $p=0.035$] and a non-significant effect of dry wet transition [$F(1,28)=0.095$, $p=0.76$] on PGF.

The simulated SGF shows that low μ subjects generate a higher SGF than the high μ subjects. It is observed that during

dry - wet transition, a higher SGF was observed in wet case as compared to dry case. Two way ANOVA shows a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28)=2.986$, $p=0.095$] and a significant effect of dry-wet transition [$F(1,28)=9.661$] on SGF.

The simulated result for average safety margin show SM to be constant for both the dry and wet condition for both high and low μ subjects. Two way ANOVA suggest a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28)=0.003$, $p=0.958$] and dry-wet transition [$F(1,28)=1.35$, $p=0.255$] on SM.

Simulated PGF/SGF ratio is lower in high μ subjects than in low μ subjects. During wetting it is observed that this ratio decreases. Using two way ANOVA, a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28)=0.162$, $p=0.69$] and significant effect of dry-wet transition [$F(1,28)=8.00$, $p=0.009$] on the PGF/SGF ratio was obtained.

DISCUSSION

The present study explains the role of skin friction changes of two kinds: 1) long term in the form of intrinsic friction, and 2) short-term in the form of acute friction change by wetting, in precision grip performance. The study involves both experimental and simulation components. Four different metrics related to precision grip performance are considered: PGF, SGF, safety margin and PGF/SGF ratio. Variations in these four metrics to due to short-term and long-term changes in friction are reported.

Experimental task

Previous studies revealed that moderate amount of skin hydration initially decreases the SGF but with increasing hydration, the SGF increases (Zackrisson, Eriksson et al. 2008; Andre, Lefevre et al. 2010). However, in the current study we found that μ decreases in all the cases of dry-wet transition. A possible explanation for this is that water forms a continuous layer which acts as a lubricant, reducing friction. It appears that the hydration levels were not so high as to show an increase in μ . Subjects with high friction show a greater decrease in μ during dry-wet

transition, than in case of low friction group. This tendency may be attributed to the absolute limit of friction for Plexiglas and finger surface ($\mu_{\text{abs}} \approx 0.4$ to 0.55) with water as lubricant.

The main reason for a high PGF is to prevent the object from slipping during the initial lifting process. We found that the PGF change from dry to wet conditions (for both high and low friction groups) is not significant. This is probably because the subject carries over an estimate of desired F_G from the dry condition and uses it effectively in the wet conditions. But when the PGF derived from the dry case is found to be inadequate, informed by the feedback which arrives after a delay, the subjects increase the F_G further, resulting in higher SGF values. On the other hand, we found that the difference in PGF between high μ subjects and low μ subjects to be significant. This suggests that PGF is dependent on the intrinsic μ . Thus, we may summarise that PGF change due to a short-term (dry/wet) change in friction is object dependent, while PGF change due to intrinsic friction is individual dependent.

SGF shows a significant change in the dry-wet transition if we lump the high and low μ subjects together. Though we observe that SGF is higher in low μ subjects compared to high μ subjects in dry conditions, the corresponding difference in wet conditions was insignificant. This observation that SGF does not show much variation between low μ subjects compared to high μ subjects under wet conditions, may perhaps have its roots in the fact that SGF, unlike PGF, is more influenced by the current friction value, which is more narrowly distributed under wet conditions. These results are in general accordance with the existing literature suggesting increase of SGF for decreasing μ (Johansson & Westling 1984; Westling & Johansson 1984; Johansson & Westling 1988; Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1991; Gordon, Forssberg et al. 1991; Forssberg, Eliasson et al. 1995; Johansson 1999; Saels, Thonnard et al. 1999; Zhang & Mak 1999; Andre, Lefevre et al. 2009).

The average value of SM was maintained in a very narrow band for all the four categories of interest: low and high μ subjects and for dry/wet conditions. The result suggests that SM

is more dependent on the object rather than the friction or the individual

The average PGF/SGF ratio is nearly the same for both low μ subjects and high μ subjects under the dry condition, whereas the ratio is lower for high μ subjects than for low μ subjects under wet conditions. A natural explanation to this trend is the fact that PGF is nearly the same between dry and wet conditions, while SGF is higher in wet conditions.

In some grip profiles, F_G has no peak grip force in the short term; F_G rises gradually to a steady state value (Figure 7). This type of F_G profile was not reported previously. Only one subject in the dry case generated the “SGF > PGF” type of profile and five subjects in wet case showed this type of profile. It is possible that the subjects employ one of two strategies (PGF > SGF and PGF < SGF) for F_G generation and a low friction condition favours selection of SGF > PGF profile. We pointed out earlier that the change in PGF due to dry/wet transition is not significant. This is probably because the PGF is determined by the prior experience with the object, whereas SGF is determined in real-time by feedback related to object slippage. If the initial estimate of the required grip force is high, the grip force profile visits a peak value and then comes to a stable value (Figure 2). On the other hand, if the initial estimates are too low, the grip force will continue to build up beyond the initial estimate, creating a profile in which there is no peak.

Table 3. *Presents a summary of PGF, SGF, SM and PGF/SGF due to long-term (High μ Vs low μ) and short-term (Dry case Vs wet case) changes in μ .*

	High μ Vs low μ	Dry case Vs wet case
PGF	SD	ND
SGF	ND	SD
SM	ND	ND
PGF/SGF	ND	SD

Note: Here, SD represents significant difference and ND represent non-significant difference.

Computational model

The proposed computational model generates accurate results (errors <1%) for both dry and wet cases for all the 16 subjects when full training was provided. However, higher error was observed in partial training of $PID_{KG,wet}$. In all the cases of partial training, the safety margin prevents the object from slipping. The partial training helps the subjects to rapidly adapt to the change in μ . This explains how the rapid training enables successful lift when the μ reduces drastically. The normal dry condition controller parameters may be trained over many encounters with different objects but under suddenly reduced μ the controller parameters for dry case may be used as an initial for controller training.

A revealing feature of the model is that PID_{KL} is the same for both dry and wet conditions, whereas PID_{KG} is retrained (both partially and fully) for wet conditions. The fact that the same controller for F_L works well for both dry and wet conditions, while the F_G controller needs to be retrained, suggests that the neural substrates for lifting and precision grip are probably different. fMRI-based studies on neural substrates of PG performance shed some light on this point (Ehrsson, Fagergren et al. 2001; Ehrsson, Fagergren et al. 2003). Ehrsson et al (2001) found preferential activation of bilateral cortex lining the inferior part of the precentral sulcus, the rostral cingulate motor area, and the right intraparietal cortex when the subjects were engaged in precision grip tasks. A subsequent study (Ehrsson et al 2003), considered three tasks related to precision grip generation: 1) the grip-load force task in which the subjects both grip and lift the object, 2) the grip force task in which the subjects only grip the object without lifting it, and 3) the load force task in which the subjects lift the object, without gripping it, by pressing upwards against a horizontal yoke fixed to the top of the object. When activation produced during the grip-load force task was compared with that of grip force alone, there was preferential activation of a part of posterior IntraParietal Sulcus (IPS). However, when activation produced during the grip-load force task was compared with that of load force alone, there was activation in right prefrontal area, in addition to the same part of

posterior IPS activated in the previous case. These results indicate that it is possible to double-dissociate the respective substrates of lifting and gripping in precision grip performance (Ehrsson, Fagergren et al. 2001; Ehrsson, Fagergren et al. 2003).

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ANNEXURE A

Calibration of the F_G strain gauge. The steps involved in strain gauge calibration was as follows:

1. One end of the cantilever beam having the load cell was fixed to the object and force was applied at the other end.
2. The force was applied by placing the constant weights on the sensor plate and obtaining the corresponding voltages.
3. The signals from the sensors were amplified by the non-inverting amplifier, filtered and fed to the data acquisition card. The gain for the sensor was fixed at 826.5 and first order low pass filter was set to 16Hz.

Figure A1. Calibration curve for input load and output voltage for FG strain gauge

The load output relationship is given as Figure A1

Where, trend line equation is

$$\text{Output} = 0.0018 * \text{Load} + 0.074 ; R^2 = 0.9979$$

Table A1. Showing the PID_{KL} , $PID_{KG,dry}$, $PID_{KG,wet}$ (F) and $PID_{KG,wet}$ (P). Here (F) and (P) means fully trained values and partially trained values. Please not that for the $PID_{KG,dry}$, $PID_{KG,wet}$ (F) and $PID_{KG,wet}$ (P) the following parameters were kept constant $K_D=9$, $\tau_F=0.06$ and $\tau_E=0.8$.

Subject	PID_{KL}					$PID_{KG,dry}$		$PID_{KG,wet}$ (F)		$PID_{KG,wet}$ (P)	
	K_P	K_I	K_D	τ_F		K_P	K_I	K_P	K_I	K_P	K_I
S1	6.938	14.484	1.387	0.087		252.152	200.126	158.607	188.145	159.873	186.960
S2	6.902	14.485	1.374	0.093		491.372	410.776	322.199	295.565	302.975	307.718
S3	7.158	15.377	1.368	0.092		236.193	336.964	240.193	365.660	244.630	352.900
S4	7.364	14.485	1.461	0.092		478.754	323.398	276.244	210.805	271.363	214.305
S5	7.306	14.583	1.378	0.088		686.356	478.244	341.775	331.647	333.973	319.742
S6	7.149	14.717	1.461	0.092		783.010	336.041	328.711	188.655	341.886	175.954
S7	7.024	14.920	1.361	0.089		626.208	427.773	264.478	211.547	260.712	206.484
S8	7.224	14.667	1.463	0.092		600.500	655.099	308.586	417.765	302.755	434.961
S9	7.018	14.808	1.450	0.086		376.451	343.181	191.639	248.837	199.302	242.366
S10	6.930	15.499	1.400	0.092		697.989	413.571	326.614	257.795	346.688	247.251
S11	6.991	15.247	1.428	0.090		865.885	453.508	255.885	260.508	268.837	270.775
S12	6.941	14.707	1.471	0.088		584.350	430.226	274.350	250.226	280.407	258.553
S13	6.761	14.990	1.441	0.088		573.859	311.240	293.859	229.854	300.754	227.367
S14	6.921	14.616	1.475	0.088		529.544	409.917	252.498	232.909	256.789	243.424
S15	6.734	15.446	1.404	0.092		543.002	431.916	291.032	268.916	287.837	281.056
S16	7.168	15.296	1.434	0.087		678.200	460.483	192.015	235.002	181.704	242.915

ANNEXURE C

Figure A2. Figure illustrating the change in K_p , K_i , K_d and τ_{FL} for PID_{KL} and change in cost function, C_L ; mean object position, \bar{X}_o ; peak object position max X_o , and variance in object position, σ_x . Each bar represents the mean \pm SD for subjects S1 and S16.

Figure A3. Figure illustrating the change in K_P , K_I (keeping K_D , $\tau_{E,G}$ and $\tau_{F,G}$ constant) for $PID_{K_G,dry}$ and cost function for F_G controller (C_G), peak grip force (PGF), steady state grip force (SGF) and slip distance (distance between the finger and object position). Each bar represents the mean \pm SD for subjects S1 and S16.

Figure A4. Figure illustrating the change in K_P , K_I , (keeping K_D , $\tau_{E,G}$ and $\tau_{F,G}$ constant) for $PID_{K_G, wet}$ and cost function for F_G controller (C_G), peak grip force (PGF), steady state grip force (SGF) and slip distance (distance between the finger and object position). Each bar represents the mean \pm SD for subjects S1 and S16.

APPENDIX

Derivation of F_{noslip}

$$F_{fin} = F_L - F_f - M_{fin}g \quad \dots \text{from Eqn. (9)}$$

$$F_o = F_f + F_n - M_o g \quad \dots \text{from Eqn. (10)}$$

In case of no slip i.e. $a_{fin} = a_o$, F_f is replaced by F_{noslip} .

Equating $a_{\text{fin}} = a_o$, or $\frac{F_{\text{fin}}}{M_{\text{fin}}} = \frac{F_o}{M_o}$, we get

$$\frac{F_L}{M_{\text{fin}}} - \frac{F_{\text{noslip}}}{M_{\text{fin}}} - \frac{M_{\text{fin}}g}{M_{\text{fin}}} = \frac{F_{\text{noslip}}}{M_o} + \frac{F_n}{M_o} - \frac{M_o g}{M_o}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{F_L}{M_{\text{fin}}} - \frac{F_{\text{noslip}}}{M_{\text{fin}}} = \frac{F_{\text{noslip}}}{M_o} + \frac{F_n}{M_o}$$

$$\text{Or, } F_{\text{noslip}} = \frac{M_o M_{\text{fin}}}{M_o + M_{\text{fin}}} \left(\frac{F_L}{M_{\text{fin}}} - \frac{F_n}{M_o} \right) \quad \dots(12)$$

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